

leaves. Although all crop stages are susceptible, the infestation rate and feeding are heavier in nurseries about to be transplanted and in the early transplanted crop. During heavy incidence, almost all leaves are infested. Feeding symptoms are narrow linear holes in the interveinal areas that leave the veins intact. Such holes are

distributed along the entire leaf lamina and resemble those made by grasshoppers.

A field trial was conducted to determine suitable insecticides for controlling crickets as well as other insects. Six insecticide granules were tried at 2 levels:

- Carbofuran at 0.5 kg and 1.0 kg a.i./ha
- Phorate at 1.0 kg and 2.0 kg a.i./ha

- Mephosfolan at 0.5 kg and 1.0 kg a.i./ha
- Disulfoton at 1.0 kg and 2.0 kg a.i./ha
- Quinalphos at 1.0 kg and 2.0 kg a.i./ha
- Chlordimeform hydrochloride at 0.5 kg and 1.0 kg a.i./ha.

Of these carbofuran at 1.0 kg a.i./ha was the most effective in pest control, followed by phorate at 2.0 kg a.i./ha. ■

Occurrence of the rice ear-cutting caterpillar in the Punjab of Pakistan

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The rice ear-cutting caterpillar *Pseudaletia unipuncta* has never been a serious rice pest in the Punjab Province of Pakistan. The first observation of serious damage was reported on berseem fodder (*Trifolium alexandrinum*) in 1972. That crop is sown after rice harvest in the rice tract of Pakistan. At that time only a few larvae and pupae are observed in rice stubble. An unusual upsurge of the pest was noticed in the area of the Institute in October and November. Attacks of the pest were also recorded in Narang and Kamoke areas (Sheikhupura District). The pest attacked the rice crop when routine insecticide applications were halted after the third week of September.

Observations of ear-cutting caterpillars, Punjab, Pakistan.

Variety	Visual assessment of damaged panicles (%)	Insects (av no./hill)
BR2360-6-5-1-10	95	5.4
BR51-46-5	90	4.6
IET6073	70	1.8
BP919-24-7-1	50	2.2
B541-B-KN-22-7-2	30	3.0
B441-B-126-3-2-1	15	1.2
B541-B-KN58-5-3	10	1.6
IET3363	5	1.4

The larvae damaged some varieties considerably. The insect preferred semidwarf varieties, particularly those that were relatively green. Panicles of such varieties were completely denuded.

Observations on the number of insects per hill were recorded in a field sown to different varieties. Five hills per sample were checked. The results are in the table.

From 1.2 to 5.4 insects/hill, averaging

2.6/hill. were present (see table). As expected, varieties with more insects were damaged more; the soil surface was completely covered with cut panicles and grains.

In a preliminary trial, dusting the crop with a mixture of BHC (0.25 kg a.i./ha) + DDT (0.75 kg a.i./ha) killed 95% of the larvae within 24 hours of the application. Water was completely drained before dusting. ■

Two subterranean pests of upland rice in Papua New Guinea

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Two rice pests newly identified in Papua New Guinea can severely damage upland rice in the seedling and tillering stages.

Infestation symptoms are similar to those of kresek, a systemic symptom caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae*. Seedlings that are attacked at an early age die, and more mature plants that are attacked have fewer tillers and fewer spikelets per panicle. The younger tillers are affected most severely. Widespread infestation

can destroy as much as 90% of the crop.

Caenoblissus pilosus (Hemiptera: Lygaeidae), a chinch bug previously reported from the western Carolines, is related to *Blissus* sp., a pest of maize, small grains, and turf grasses.

In appearance and life cycle it is similar to *Blissus* sp. At the youngest stage it is 0.7 mm long. At adult stage, the insect is about 3 mm long, with silver wings on a black body. At the juvenile stage it is red with black markings.

Chinch bugs inhabit the root zone immediately adjacent to the base of the plant within 1 or 2 cm of the soil surface. They may be visible on the soil surface in the early morning or late afternoon.

Mealy bugs (family Pseudococcidae)

have also been observed in most fields that are attacked by chinch bugs. They are often found on nearby plants, but not on the same plants as chinch bugs. Ants, which tend the mealy bugs, are usually present on the soil surface at the base of the plant.

The adult mealy bug is 2.5 cm long and off-white to pink. Both the chinch bug and the mealy bug damage the plant by extracting moisture and nutrients from the roots. They also attack maize and sorghum, but because the infestation level is lower, damage symptoms are not visible.

Puspalum sp. and other soft-stemmed grasses are alternate hosts of the chinch bug.

Chinch bugs and mealy bugs have been observed damaging rice in New Ireland, East New Britain, Morobe, Madang, and Central Provinces. Probably they are widely distributed throughout the lower elevations of Papua New Guinea.

No effective control measures have been determined, although the chinch bug is known to be susceptible to lindane (gamma-BHC). Spraying of the affected plant and of the soil at the plant's base has been unsuccessful, but seed

treatments with appropriate pesticides may be suitable. Additional studies to determine appropriate control techniques are required if the area planted to upland rice expands. ■

Rice leaf miner damage — a problem in Guyana

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The rice leaf miner was first noted as a serious rice pest in Guyana in 1975. Leaf miner epidemics have since occurred regularly, especially on late-sown crops. Recent surveys have revealed that only one species of *Hydrellia* (Diptera: Ephydriidae) (described by the author as

H. deonieri n. sp.) is endemic to Guyana and damages rice throughout the rice-growing belt. Damage can appear as a deadheart, mining, and dying of leaves on plants 7 to 32 days old. Damaged plants are stunted and less vigorous, and yields are reduced. The main reasons for the increasing importance of this pest are presumed to be a change in cultural practices (from dry to wet sowing) and the introduction of double-cropping.

Two rice crops per year are now

grown in Guyana: the main or autumn crop, harvested June–July, and the small or spring crop, harvested in December–January. Young rice seedlings that can be mined by the pest are present for a maximum of 3 to 4 months annually. A number of alternate host plants, all of the family Gramineae, help maintain the population level during the off-crop season. All varieties grown in Guyana are susceptible. In severe attacks, fields up to 40 ha have been completely destroyed. ■

An inexpensive kerosene light trap to monitor rice insects

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An inexpensive kerosene light trap tested in Philippine rice fields in 1978 is highly attractive to the following insects: *Tryporyza incertulas*, *T. innotata*, *Chilo suppressalis*, *Sesamia inferens*, *Nymphula depunctalis*, *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis*, *Nilaparvata lugens*, *Nephotettix virescens*, *N. nigropictus*, *Sogatella furcifera*, *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis*, *Naranga aenescens*, and *Rivula nr. atimeta*. The lantern is an improvement of that presented in the 1970 Rice production manual.

The light source is a fisherman's kerosene lantern designed for outdoor use. Village tinsmiths can easily make it with locally available materials. Each lantern costs about US\$4. It uses only a few cents worth of kerosene per night and produces a bright white light. The funnel-shaped exhaust cap extends 4 cm down into the lantern body and efficiently removes the small amount of soot that accumulates on the inside of the glass (see figure). Rain does not affect the lantern's performance. The lantern, attached to a wooden or bamboo support frame, hangs above the rice crop.

1. Design of the lantern with handle. IRR I Entomology Department.

The frame has a platform that supports a basin of water (see photo). Cooking oil that is added covers the water surface

The kerosene lantern can be made inexpensively from local materials. IRR I Entomology Department.

and immobilizes fallen insects. Experience shows that baffles are not necessary. The insects hit the lantern and fall into the water basin below.

Farmers who have been taught to recognize each important species can recover and count insects daily. We are now correlating daily catches with field populations. We hope that farmers and extension technicians can use the trap as a tool in forecasting. ■